

IPBES invasive alien species assessment, data management report for Chapter 3. Section 3.2.2.4: Urbanization

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Description

Section 3.2.2.4 assesses the role of urbanisation as drivers of biological invasions in Chapter 3 of IPBES thematic assessment of invasive alien species and their control. The experts conducted a systematic review to report on the existing knowledge on this driver. This systematic review consists in the main source of evidence for the section.

Process overview

Search 1:

Search 2:

Search 3:

Search 4:

Search 5:

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** literature review

- **Search language(s):** English

- **Search terms:**

Search 1: (urban* AND inva* OR alien OR exotic) filtered by "ecology"

Search 2: (urban* AND inva* OR alien OR exotic AND driver AND vector AND ecology) filtered by "city"

Search 3: (urban* AND inva* OR alien OR exotic AND driver AND vector AND ecology AND marine) filtered by "100 most recent"

Search 4: (urban AND global AND definition AND ecology)

Search 5: (urban AND heat islands AND invasi*)

- **Search engine:** Web of Science

-**Searched time period:**

Search 1: 2009 to 2019

Search 2: 2014 to 2019

Search 3: 2014 to 2019

Search 4: 1900 to 2019

Search 5: 1900 to 2019

- **Date:**

Search 1: 10 October 2019

Search 2: 10 October 2019

Search 3: 14 October 2019

Search 4: 12 November 2019

Search 5: 11 December 2019

- **Overview of the search results and selection criteria:**

Number of search result:

Search 1: 180 (4 papers selected for review)

Search 2: 22 (2 papers selected for review)

Search 3: 100 (4 papers selected for review)

Search 4: 17 (1 paper selected for review)

Search 5: 24 (1 paper selected for review)

Selection criteria:

Articles that specified urbanisation as a vector of introduction of IAS

Number of added papers (experts' knowledge and reviewers' recommendations):

None

- **Step by step analysis (methodology, categories, etc.):**

Number of papers reviewed:

From the initial 343 papers found, the first scan included reviewing from the title and abstracts which ones were the most representative for the section, the ones that could include information of urbanisation as a vector of introduction for IAS were fully read, and then 12 were selected to draft the section. Diversity on ecosystems and stages of the invasive process was prioritised.

Following the first internal review, reviewers suggested eight more papers to increase geographical diversity.

Fields extracted:

- Publication title
- Year of publication
- Invasion stage [Uptake and transport; Introduction; Establishment; Spread]
- Biomes [Terrestrial; Freshwater; Marine]
- Taxon [Plant; Vertebrate; Invertebrate; Microbes]
- Type of study [Primary study; Review; Meta-analysis]
- Region [Europe and Central Asia; Asia-Pacific; Oceania; Americas; Africa]
- Unit of analysis [IPBES units of analysis]
- Cross-cutting theme [Scenarios and models; indigenous and local knowledge; Good quality of life]
- Comment (free text)

- Files (code, review templates, etc.):

[Chapter 3 literature review masterdatabase.xlsx](#)